

RESULTS OF FEED CONVERSION, DAILY GAIN AVERAGE THICKNESS OF THE BACK AND SIDE BACON AND PERCENT OF MEAT IN PERFORMANCE TEST OF BOARS LANDRACE RACE (PHENOTYPIC PARAMETERS)*

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SUMMARY: To achieve a larger and more profitable production, breeding goal in swine production has to be focused on the repair of all economically important traits. It is important that in addition to good nutrition, care and keeping conditions, use of the best breeding animals, which is achieved by proper selection of the organization of work, selection of animals base d on test results and assessments of breeding values with modern methods to ensure high accuracy. Analyzed the performance characteristics of the test boars Landrace breeds such as: Dutch, Swedish, German and Danish, originating from several farms in Vojvodina, in order to analyze the variability of different traits. Phenotypic variability properties of the aggregate genotype is high and within the quoted literature. Phenotypic variability properties of the aggregate genotype is high and within the quoted literature. Identified a statistically significant difference in the thickness of the side of bacon and meat percentage ($p < 0.05$) and Duncan test were statistically significant differences in the thickness of back fat between Danish Landrace and other (Dutch, Swedish and German 8,60:14,37, 13.22 and 13.18 mm, $p < 0.05$), then the thickness of the side fat between the Dutch and Danish (14,78:10,60, $p < 0.05$) and the percentage of meat between the Danish and other Landrace (Dutch, Swedish and German 64,29:58,27, 59.62 and 58.79; $p < 0.05$). Duncan test were not statistically significant differences in feed conversion and daily gain.

Keywords: Landrace, boars, performance test, daily gain, backfat thickness, percentage of meat.

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INTRODUCTION

To achieve greater and more cost-effective production, breeding goal must be focused on the repair of all economically important traits. It is essential to improving nutrition, care and housing conditions and applying the proper selection, based on the selection of animals by test results and evaluation of breeding values with modern methods of high accuracy, which will allow us to select the best breeding animals. A significant factor in increasing production efficiency is improved pig fattening properties, which include weight gain, feed conversion and percentage of meat (Imboonta et al., 2007). These properties can be measured directly or indirectly on animals and they have medium to high heritability, which is their genetic improvement can be achieved based on test results. To select a boar, we dispose of data on the results of his test (weight gain, feed conversion, back fat thickness, meat percent, number of teats, constitution, litter size and parity from which derived) (Vidovic and Kosarcic, 1998). Candidates for selection, ie, the next generation of parents should be selected based on several characteristics (Petrovic, 1991). Merx and Oijen, (1994) show that in the Netherlands at the nucleus of selection for growth traits and carcass quality based on information obtained in performance and sib testing.

Greater intensity of selection, requires an increasing number of animals tested and therefore, in many countries use the so-called. Farm test. One of the reasons is very expensive and capacity limited testing only in the central test stations (Skolling et al., 1981; Hudson and Kennedy, 1985; Merx, 1987; Vidovic et al., 1993). At the level of commercial gilts and sows F1 generation is only phenotypic selection, without tests and experiments (Vidovic et al., 2011). Since the beginning of testing of breeding pigs to date, we were there more test methodologies, the recommendations of Markovic et al., 1963, Markovic et al., 1976, Drobnjakovic et al., 1988, Vidovic et al., 1993.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Investigations were made on four breeds Landrace boars from Vojvodina in the period since 2007. through 2011, during the performance test. Included are farms (total 18) which are registered at the Department of Animal Husbandry, Faculty of Agriculture in Novi Sad, as the Main breeding organization for AP Vojvodina. The study included a total of 699 tested Landrace boars of four breeds: Dutch (51); Sweden (337), Germany (306) and Danish Landrace (5). During the performance test, the aggregate genotype boars consisted of the following features: feed conversion (FC, kg) daily gain (DP, kg), average back fat thickness, (LS, mm), average thickness of the side of bacon, (BS, mm) and the percentage of meat, (PM, %).

Rating phenotypic parameters was performed in the program "Statistics 10" as follows: mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation, minimum and maximum values, analysis of variance and Duncanov test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Average values and variability of phenotypic expression of traits in the aggregate genotype in 699 boars performance tested, originating from 18 farms in Vojvodina are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Average values and variability of the traits of boars tested (699 boars tested)
 Tabela 1. Prosečne vrednosti i varijabilnost ispitivanih osobina kod 699 testiranih nerastova

Traits / Osobina	$\bar{X}$	σ_X	σ	σ^2	CV%	Min	Max
FC,kg	2,28	0,01	0,33	0,12	14,86	1,45	4,83
DG, kg	0,827	0,005	0,136	0,0186	16,48	0,328	1,365
LS, mm	13,25	0,18	4,85	23,55	36,60	5,00	28,00
BS, mm	12,94	0,18	4,80	23,06	37,09	5,00	26,00
PM, %	59,19	0,17	4,62	21,37	7,80	44,07	72,33

In Table 1 we see that the average feed conversion of all boars in the performance test was 2.28 ± 0.01 kg, daily gain of 0.827 ± 0.005 kg, back fat thickness of 13.25 ± 0.18 mm, thick side of bacon 12.94 ± 0.18 mm and the percentage of meat in carcass $59.19 \pm 0.17\%$. Examining the performance test boars from Vojvodina, Jakovljević et al., (1987) found that the feed conversion in the test since 1982. to 1986. was reduced from 2.89 kg to 2.80 kg, an average of more test race and combinations. If we look at our results, we see that the conversion is drastically reduced (2.28) compared to the conversion in 1987. year.

According to the Short et al., (1994), the mean value for daily weight gain ranged from 770.4 to 868.2 g, which is consistent with our results (0.827 kg). The same author states that the average back fat thickness ranged from 11.6 mm to 14.7 mm, while in our data the average value was 13.25 mm and feed conversion of 2.16 kg to 2.31 kg, while in our results, feed conversion was 2.28 kg. Approximate results and other authors (Trivunović, 1996; Brkic et al., 2000; Mijatovic et al., 2006).

In Graph 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 is shown a trend KH, DP, LS, BS and PM since 2007. - 2011. year.

Graph. 1. The average feed conversion performance test
 Graf. 1. Prosečna konverzija hrane u performans testu

Graph. 2. Average daily gain in performance test Landrace since 2007-2011
 Graf. 2. Prosečan dnevni prirast u performans testu landrasa od 2007.-2011.

Graf 3. Prosečna debljina leđne slanine u performans
 Graph. 3. The average thickness of back fat Landrace

Graf 4. Prosečna debljina bočne slanine u performans testu landrasa od 2007-2011.
 Graph. 4. The average thickness of the side of bacon Landrace performance test since 2007-2011.

Graph. 5. The average percentage of meat in the performance test Landrace since 2007.- 2011.
 Graf. 5. Prosečan procenat mesa u performans testu landrasa od 2007. – 2011.

In Graph. 2. we see a slight decrease DP since 2009. to 2010. sharply declining in 2011. years with extreme variability. The research Mijatovic et al., (2006), according to average daily gain in Swedish Landrace, Large White and Duroc in the period since 1995. to 2011.year had a declining trend. Shown in graph 3 and 4 is observed a slight increase in the average value of LS and BS by 2010. with a decrease in 2011. while the PM had a steady decrease (Graph 5). With all the traits expressed the large variability in 2011. year. Mijatovic et al., (2006), indicate that the early years of the test was statistically highly significant ($P < 0.001$) and resulted in the variation of all traits of food utilization and almost all the investigated fattening properties, except for the duration of the test and the average daily gain

The content of meat in the carcass is one of the main indicators of quality of carcass. Timanovic, (2003), Tomovic, (2000), Petrovic, Milica and Pusic, (2004), Petrovic, Milica et al., (2006), Radovic et al., (2007) indicate a fairly consistent results on the content of meat in carcass (from 41.71 to 43.32%) which does not agree with the results of this study, where he established a general average content in the carcass meat for all breeds of Landrace 59.19 % with variation of 44.07 to 72.33%.

Average values and variability of phenotypic expression of traits in the aggregate genotype in Dutch and Swedish Landrace is shown in Table 2 and 3.

Table 2. Average values and variability of the traits of Dutch Landrace breed of 51-th tested boars

Tabela 2. Prosečne vrednosti i varijabilnost ispitivanih osobina holandskog landrasa (51 nerast)

Traits / Osobina	$\bar{X}$	σ_X	σ	σ^2	CV,%	Min	Max
FC,kg	2,31	0,03	0,28	0,07	12,11	1,78	2,88
DG, kg	0,792	0,013	0,096	0,0092	12,20	0,554	0,993
LS, mm	14,37	0,72	5,21	27,15	36,25	5,00	28,00
BS, mm	14,78	0,75	5,39	29,09	36,48	5,00	26,00
PM, %	58,27	0,80	5,78	33,41	9,91	47,97	72,33

Table 3. Average values and variability of the traits in the breed Swedish Landrace (337 boars tested)

Tabela 3. Prosečne vrednosti i varijabilnost ispitivanih osobina za rasu švedski landras (337 nerastova)

Traits / Osobina	$\bar{X}$	σ_X	σ	σ^2	CV,%	Min	Max
FC,kg	2,24	0,02	0,36	0,14	16,47	1,50	4,83
DG, kg	0,836	0,007	0,142	0,0201	16,98	0,328	1,365
LS, mm	13,22	0,27	4,99	24,96	37,76	5,00	28,00
BS, mm	12,73	0,26	4,88	23,82	38,33	5,00	26,00
PM, %	59,62	0,24	4,50	20,26	7,54	44,07	72,19

The average feed conversion in Dutch and Swedish Landrace amounted to 2.31 ± 0.03 and 2.24 ± 0.02 kg. The standard deviation for this trait was 0.28 and 0.36 kg, with a coefficient of variation of 12.11 and 16.47%. Average daily gain for the Dutch and Swedish Landrace was 0.792 ± 0.013 , 0.836 ± 0.007 kg, the absolute variations of the Dutch from 0.554 to 0.993 and 0.328 kg to 1.365 kg in Swedish Landrace. The average thickness of back fat in Dutch Landrace was 14.37 ± 0.72 and 13.22 in Sweden ± 0.27 mm, the coefficient of variation of 36.25 and 37.76%. The average thickness of the side of bacon in Dutch Landrace was 14.78 ± 0.75 mm and 12.73 ± 0.26 for the Swedish Landrace, with coefficient of variation of 34.48% and 38.33%. The resulting average feed conversion in the Swedish landras is lower than the results they get Teodorovic and Ninkov, (1972; 3.50 kg); Brkic et al., (2000; 2.74 kg); Mijatovic et al., (2005; 2.42 kg). Average daily gain was lower than in daily gain that received Brkic et al., (2000; 0.871 kg), Johnson et al., (2002) and Mijatovic et al., (2005; 0.865 kg). The average percentage of meat in the carcass of the Dutch Landrace, was $58.27 \pm 0.80\%$, with coefficient of variation of 9.91% and $59.62 \pm 0.24\%$ Swedish Landrace, with coefficient of variation of 7.54%.

Average values and variability of phenotypic expression of traits in the aggregate genotype in German and Danish Landrace is shown in Table 4 and 5.

Table 4. Average values and variability of the traits in the breed German Landrace (306 boars tested)

Tabela 4. Prosečne vrednosti i varijabilnost ispitivanih osobina nemačkog landrasa (306 nerastova)

Traits / Osobina	$\bar{X}$	σ_X	σ	σ^2	CV%	Min	Max
FC,kg	2,31	0,01	0,31	0,10	13,38	1,45	3,04
DG, kg	0,824	0,007	0,1341	0,0179	16,27	0,418	1,197
LS, mm	13,18	0,26	4,61	21,32	35,02	5,00	27,00
BS, mm	12,91	0,26	4,58	21,03	35,50	5,00	26,00
PM, %	58,79	0,25	4,47	19,99	7,06	47,04	71,98

Table 5. Average values and variability of the traits of the Danish Landrace breed (5 boars tested)

Tabela 5. Prosečne vrednosti i varijabilnost ispitivanih osobina danskog landrasa (5 nerastova)

Traits / Osobina	$\bar{X}$	σ_x	σ	σ^2	CV%	Min	Max
FC,kg	2,41	0,07	0,17	0,03	7,35	2,21	2,63
DG, kg	0,824	0,091	0,205	0,0421	24,90	0,460	0,934
LS, mm	8,60	0,97	2,19	4,80	25,47	5,00	10,00
BS, mm	10,0	0,74	1,67	2,80	15,78	8,00	12,00
PM, %	64,29	1,63	3,65	13,39	5,69	59,25	68,25

The average feed conversion in the German and Danish Landrace was 2.31 ± 0.01 and 2.41 ± 0.07 kg. The standard deviation for this trait was 0.31 and 0.17 kg, with a coefficient of variation of 13.38 and 7.35%. Average daily gain in the German and Danish Landrace was 0.824 ± 0.007 ; 0.824 ± 0.091 kg, with absolute variations in German Landrace from 0.418 to 1.197 and 0.460 to 0.934 kg in the Danish Landrace.

The average thickness of back fat in German Landrace was 13.18 ± 0.26 mm, and the Danish 8.60 ± 0.97 mm, with coefficient of variation of 35.02 and 25.47%. The average thickness of the side of bacon was 12.91 ± 0.26 mm for German and 10.00 ± 0.74 mm for the Danish Landrace, with coefficient of variation of 35.50% and 15.78%. The average percentage of meat in the carcass of German Landrace was $58.79 \pm 0.25\%$, the coefficient of variation of 7.06% and in the Danish Landrace $64.29 \pm 1.63\%$, the coefficient of variation of 5.69%.

Table 6. Analysis of variance of the traits in the aggregate genotype

Tabela 6. Analiza varijanse ispitivanih osobina u agregatnom genotipu

Traits / Osobina	SS - race <i>SS - rase</i>	df-race <i>df-rase</i>	MS - race <i>MS - rase</i>	SS - errors <i>SS - greške</i>	df- errors <i>df - greške</i>	MS - errors <i>MS - greške</i>	F	P
FC, kg	296,5432	3	98,84773	115511,2	695	166,2032	0,594740	0,618594
DG, kg	117218,2	3	39072,7	15178741	695	21839,9	1,789052	0,147867
LS, mm	173,9	3	58,0	16264	695	23,4	2,476328	0,060322
BS, mm	215,9	3	72,0	15882	695	22,9	3,149103	0,02453*
PM, %	277,0	3	92,3	15848	695	22,8	4,048626	0,00721*

* Marked effects are significant at $p < 0.050$, *Vrednosti su statistički značajne $p < 0,050$

**SS-sums of squares df-degrees of freedom, MS-square environment **SS-sume kvadrata; df-stepeni slobode; MS-sredine kvadrata

Analysis of variance (Table 6) were found statistically significant differences in BS, PM ($p < 0.05$) and Duncan test were statistically significant differences in LS (Table 7) between the Danish and Dutch, Swedish, German Landrace (8.60 : 14.37, 13.22 and 13.18 mm, $p < 0.05$), the BS (Table 7), between the Dutch and Danish Landrace (14,78:10,60, $p < 0.05$) and PM (Table 9) between the Danish and Dutch, Swedish, German Landrace (64,29:58,27, 59.62 and 58.79, $p < 0.05$). Duncan test were not statistically significant differences in the FC and DG.

Table 7. Duncan test for LS, BS and PM
 Tabela 7. Duncanov test za LS, BS i PM

LS / LS	Dutch / Holandski $\bar{X}$ 14,37	Swedish / Švedski $\bar{X}$ 13,22	German / Nemački $\bar{X}$ 13,18	Danish / Danski $\bar{X}$ 8,60
Dutch / Holandski		0,481577	0,494649	0,000729*
Swedish / Švedski	0,481577		0,977698	0,006154*
German / Nemački	0,494649	0,977698		0,004830*
Danish / Danski	0,000729*	0,006154*	0,004830*	
BS / BS	Dutch / Holandski $\bar{X}$ 14,78	Swedish / Švedski $\bar{X}$ 12,73	German / Nemački $\bar{X}$ 12,91	Danish / Danski $\bar{X}$ 10,60
Holandski/Dutch		0,230019	0,244567	0,015383*
Švedski/Swedish	0,230019		0,908293	0,184865
Nemački/German	0,244567	0,908293		0,175245
Danski/Danish	0,015383*	0,184865	0,175245	
PM / PM	Dutch / Holandski $\bar{X}$ 58,27	Swedish / Švedski $\bar{X}$ 59,54	German / Nemački $\bar{X}$ 58,72	Danish / Danski $\bar{X}$ 64,29
Holandski/Dutch		0,462113	0,779219	0,000346*
Švedski/Swedish	0,462113		0,611988	0,003068*
Nemački/German	0,779219	0,611988		0,000765*
Danski/Danish	0,000346*	0,003068*	0,000765*	

* Marked effects are significant at $p < 0.050$ * Vrednosti su statistički značajne $p < 0,050$

The difference that is established between the Danish Landrace and others into the LS, BS and PM is the result of a small number of boars performance tested.

Lundeheim and Eriksson, (1984) found that the genetic improvement and the annual average daily gain in the Landrace breed test amounted to 6.0 g and feed consumption per kilogram of weight gain was reduced by 0.032 g, as a result of the direction and intensity of selection. Suzuki et al., (1991) analyzed data for 141 and 136 are not castrated boars of Landrace breeds, selected for 10 generations on the basis of the index to increase daily gain and back fat thickness reduction. The results showed that the increase in daily gain 19.47 g, and reduce back fat thickness of 0.04 mm per generation.

CONCLUSION

Analysis of performance test results and traits of boars included in the aggregate genotype, and based on quoted literature may be drawn the following conclusions. Average daily gain was 0.827 kg, the absolute variations that range from 0.328 to 1.365 kg. Average back fat thickness was 13.25 mm, with the absolute variation of 5.0 to 28.0 mm. Average thickness of the side of bacon was 12.94 mm, with variations from 5.00 to 26.00 mm. Established a general average content in the carcass meat for all breeds Landrace was 59.19%, with variations from 44.07 to 72.33%. Comparing the average values of medium traits in the aggregate genotype was not a statistically significant difference between the four breeds Landrace. Phenotypic trait variability is high and within the quoted literature. Such high variability suggests that it is possible to apply an intensive selection work to improve the traits in the study population.

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REZULTATI KONVERZIJE HRANE, DNEVNOG PRIRASTA, PROSEČNE DEBLJINE LEĐNE I BOČNE SLANINE I PROCENTA MESA U PERFORMANS TESTU NERASTOVA RASE LANDRAS (FENOTIPSKI PARAMETRI)

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Izvod

Oplemenjivački cilj u proizvodnji svinja usmeren je na popravku svih ekonomski važnih osobina, da bi ukupna proizvodnja bila veća i rentabilnija. Veoma važno je da pored poboljšanja ishrane, nege i uslova držanja, iz matičnih zapata iskoristiti najbolja priplodna grla, što se postiže primenom pravilne organizacije selekcijskog rada, izborom grla zasnovanog na rezultatima testiranja i ocenama oplemenjivačkih vrednosti savremenim metodama, visoke tačnosti. U radu su analizirane osobine iz performans testa nerastova rase landras i to: holandski, švedski, nemački i danski, poreklom sa farmi na teritoriji AP Vojvodine, kako bi se doneo zaključak o postojanju varijabilnosti različitih osobina. Fenotipsku varijabilnost osobina iz agregatnog genotipa je visoka i u granicama citirane literature. Utvrđene su statistički značajne razlike između landrasa u debljini bočne slanine i procentu mesa ($p < 0,05$), a Duncanovim testom su utvrđene statistički značajne razlike u debljini leđne slanine između danskog i ostalih landrasa (holandski, švedski i nemački 8,60:14,37, 13,22 i 13,18 mm; $p < 0,05$), u debljini bočne slanine između holandskog i danskog (14,78:10,60; $p < 0,05$) i u procentu mesa između danskog i ostalih landrasa (holandski, švedski i nemački 64,29:58,27; 59,62 i 58,79; $p < 0,05$). Duncanovim testom nisu utvrđene statistički značajne razlike u konverziji hrane i dnevnom prirast.

Ključne reči: landras, nerastovi, performans test, dnevni prirast, debljina slanine, procenat mesa.

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